

SEMI QUANTITATIVE ANALYZE WITH X-RAY FLUORESCENCE (XRF)

**Deliverable 3.3, SOPs for all Physicochemical Methods,
Annex I, page 216.**

Document Name ANALYTICAL METHOD		Appendix 0	Page 1 (4)
Issuer Björn Stolpe	Initial Date 2020-01-09	Rev.date	Doc. No FU035E
Printing Date 2020-05-27			
XRF ANALYSIS OF SILICA IN LIQUID FORM WITH THE ZETIUM INSTRUMENT			

1 SUMMARY

Silica products in liquid form can be analyzed with the Wroxi_liquid application.

Powdered flux is used, instead of the pre-fused flux that was used in the calibration of the method.

The method is suitable for samples in oxide form, in the concentration range shown in Table 1.

Table 1: concentration ranges (dry weight) for different oxides at 0,8 g of sample

Na ₂ O	0,05 - 60 %
MgO	0,05 - 80 %
Al ₂ O ₃	0,05 - 80 %
SiO ₂	0,1 - 100 %
P ₂ O ₅	0,05 - 40 %
SO ₃	0,05 - 60 %
K ₂ O	0,05 - 40 %
CaO	0,05 - 80 %
TiO ₂	0,05 - 40 %
MnO	0,05 - 80 %
Fe ₂ O ₃	0,05 - 100 %
ZrO ₂	0,05 - 45 %

2 GENERAL INFORMATION

This is a general instruction, based on our experiences of XRF sample preparation with lithium borate.

A copy of this instruction can be found in folder 8 in the XRF lab.

Document Name		Appendix	Page
ANALYTICAL METHOD		0	2 (4)
Issuer	Initial Date	Rev.date	Doc. No
Björn Stolpe	2020-01-09		FU035E
			Printing Date
			2020-05-27
XRF ANALYSIS OF SILICA IN LIQUID FORM WITH THE ZETIUM INSTRUMENT			

3 HAZARDS AND SAFETY

Always use protective goggles, gloves and laboratory clothes. Ensure good ventilation when working with lithium borate.

4 QUALITY ASSURANCE OF ANALYTICAL METHOD

Inspect the status of the Zetium instrument (see instruction APP002)

The method is controlled by the analysis of a certified reference material, CRM22334

Observe batch-wise the loss of powder flux after fusion.

5 APPARATUS

- 5.1 X-ray fluorescence spectrometer (Zetium, Malvern Panalytical) with Rh X-ray tube
- 5.2 Fusion instrument (LeNeo, Claisse) for sample digestion and casting of lithium borate glass disk
- 5.3 Platinum crucibles and mold
- 5.4 Pasetur pipettes (plastic)
- 5.5 Spoons (stainless steel)

6 CHEMICALS

- 6.1 Powder flux, containing 67% Lithium Tetraborate and 33 % Lithium Metaborate
- 6.2 Lithium Iodide, anhydrous, finely grinded and stored in excicator
- 6.3 CRM for quality assurance (see section 4)
- 6.4 Citric Acid for the cleaning of crucibles

Document Name		Appendix	Page	
ANALYTICAL METHOD		0	3 (4)	
Issuer	Initial Date	Rev.date	Doc. No	Printing Date
Björn Stolpe	2020-01-09		FU035E	2020-05-27
XRF ANALYSIS OF SILICA IN LIQUID FORM WITH THE ZETIUM INSTRUMENT				

7 PROCEEDURE

- 7.1 Liquid samples (aqueous solutions or slurry)
 Mix the sample
 Take a clean platinum crucible, place it on the balance and:
- 7.1.1 Add ~0,5-0,6 g of lithium iodide
- 7.1.2 Add 8,0000g ($\pm 0,0005$ g) powder flux
- 7.1.3 Add an appropriate amount of sample (depending on the SiO₂ concentration)
- 7.1.4 Mix well, dry in warming cabinet if needed
- 7.1.5 Insert the crucible in the fusion instrument and run the program "Wroxix de chauffe"
- 7.1.6 Analyze the glass disk in the XRF instrument using the application WROXI-liquid.
- 7.2 Samples containing >5 % of organic matter:
 Follow the procedure in section 7.1, but combust the sample at 600°C prior to the fusion (prior to 7.1.5)
- 7.3 Samples with concentrations above the calibration range:
 If any of the oxides has a concentration higher than the ranges shown in Table 1, repeat the analysis with a smaller amount of sample.

8 CALCULATING AND REPORTING

- 8.1 Concentrations >1 % are reported with a precision of one decimal.
 Concentrations <1 % are reported with one significant figure.

9 WASTE DISPOSAL

Residual sample is poured out in the sink or returned to the customer. The glass disk is disposed in the glass container.

10 ADDITIONAL INSTRUCTIONS

The accuracy of the method is controlled by the analysis of the certified reference material CRM 22334 every second week.

Document Name		Appendix	Page	
ANALYTICAL METHOD		0	4 (4)	
Issuer	Initial Date	Rev.date	Doc. No	Printing Date
Björn Stolpe	2020-01-09		FU035E	2020-05-27
XRF ANALYSIS OF SILICA IN LIQUID FORM WITH THE ZETIUM INSTRUMENT				

11 REFERENCES

- 11.1 Instrument instruction for the Zetium X-ray spectrometer APP002
- 11.2 Instrument instruction for the fusion instrument LeNeo APP005